

Title: Solving complex business problems from first principle basis

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the most important part of any data scientists job is to define the business problem properly and provide solutions which enables decision making and strategy formulation. But most data scientists get excited about applying latest algorithms. So, the main theme of my presentation for the first 10 is about defining problems, building consensus with business teams and spending time with IT to understand architecture/ stack to identify how designed solutions can be leveraged in scale.

AIM:

Enable Data Scientists to have a first principle based approach and ensure that business teams never get left behind

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Problem definition can be done in 3 simple steps:

- Design – This step involves clearly articulating what the current state is and what is the expected future state should be. Then we involve all business stakeholders to understand the gaps that prevent us from making the transition from current state to future state. Now the key questions which enable us to bridge those gaps are noted
- Representation – This is a mind mapping exercise. All factors which impact the key question are mapped in a hierarchical fashion. The idea here is to leave no stone unturned and ensure that data availability/ unavailability doesn't basis our thinking.
- Hypothesis – In the final step we make a hypothesis for each of the factors and clearly list the exact mathematical methods we intend to employ to test the hypothesis. Every time we prove a hypothesis we validate our business understanding and every time we disprove our hypothesis we make a discovery!

RESULTS: Clearly, defining the business problems helps us have a structured way to solve problems and having business partners on board from the get go ensures much greater consumption of the work, which is what we ultimately aim for.

CONCLUSIONS:

This method is scalable and ensures that businesses can trust the work of data scientists readily and helps us build products that can augment their capabilities

KEYWORDS:

Problem solving

BIOGRAPHY:

Shreyas is currently a data scientist at Best Buy. Best Buy is Canada's #1 omni-channel retailer and is a fortune 75 organization. Prior to this he was with the world's largest pure-play Decision Sciences firm Mu Sigma. Mu Sigma is a Sequoia funded firm and works with about 140 Fortune 500 firms. With Mu Sigma, he worked for 3 Fortune 100 organizations both as a data scientist and as a leader of a team of scientists. He holds a MBA from UBC, ranked in the top 50 MBA programs in the world and an electrical engineering degree from India.